

Systematic Architecture to Indian Languages Massive Open Online Course (SAIL-MOOC)

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ABSTRACT

In the recent years, the concept of distant learning and online courses are gaining huge attention from students' across the globe. And such courses also promote young individuals to experience quality learning towards higher education. The unique feature of MOOC is providing education to public, at minimum level of cost at large scale and to deliver an attestation of completion to those who fulfill their study. In order to establish an all-round quality, affordability, scalability, inclusion and employability education, SAIL-MOOC is a state-of-the-art to Massive Open Online Courses program through Indian Languages. It would be an online environment where learning is centered on collaborating, creating connections and resolving queries through continual cognition in Indian language preferably in a classic regional language Odia.

INTRODUCTION

Adaptive Learning is the other major educational technology development over the past few years. However to provide learners an opportunity to build a sustainable portfolio for lifelong learning, no such means yet to prove to be qualified such level. Again to improve the quality and scale of tertiary education in developing countries like India, infrastructure to multilingual digital contents and local context to its outcomes across sectors are going to be important to establish. Massive Open Online Courses (MOOC) is the latest buzz vocabulary offers an alternative to lecture-mode classroom instruction using digital content. Through this course students can download their course anytime, anywhere depending upon their convenience. However the Indian local language like Odia, even if after a status of Classical language, yet to be more steps required in this area. No any visible demarcating MOOC product using Odia language is available for Odia language learner students as well as Native mother tongue migrants. For this purpose here we are trying to establish a four phased circular

and business Module MOOC (i.e SAIL-MOOC) for the learners in order to establish a dynamic teaching learning free-flung environment.

What is a MOOC?

A MOOC (Massive Open Online Course) is a free, open access and scalable online higher education courses for large scale participation. It is an extension of existing online learning or adaptive learning approaches. The aim of the MOOC is to provide lifelong learning and development to virtually everyone, anytime, anywhere in the world with internet access. MOOCs offer free online courses covering wide range of topics delivered by qualified lecturers from some of the most well-known universities in the world. It enables people with an interest in a selected topic to study and learn through interaction with others of similar interest. It provides an opportunity for people in remote areas and developing countries as well as people with aspirations to achieve more with their lives. The established MOOC teaching learning environment may help to lower the cost of

higher education which attracts the learners looking for lower cost education.

MOOCs started as a form of collaborative online learning with people interacting and learning from each other and being exposed to different perspectives, views and ideas. Now-a-days many high profile and elite universities are now offering their standard courses as open courses. A growing number of institutions have been involved in engaging and experimenting with MOOCs for the purpose of expanding access, marketing and branding, as well as the potential of developing new revenue streams.

Literature Survey:

The first MOOC phenomenon was introduced by George Siemens, Stephen Downes and David Cormier called as Connectivism and Connective Knowledge 2008 (CCK08). In international level the major players like Coursera, Udacity and Edx witness high number of enrollments from India. Coursera i.e. consider as a standard MOOC (sMOOC), introduced its official mobile app for iPhone on December 17, 2013. edX: edX offers interactive online classes and MOOCs from the world's best universities. Its online courses are from MITx, HarvardX, BerkeleyX, UTx and many other universities.

In national market, a MOOC on software architecture and cloud computing was conceptualized and offered IIT, Kanpur, in conjunction with the Commonwealth of Learning in Vancouver, recently completed the delivery of its second MOOC entitled, "Mobiles for Development", or M4D. The course material was offered at three levels: one, it was open for anyone to browse; two, learners would need to register to attempt the assignments; and three, the learners would need to pay a registration fee of INR 900 to get a certificate. IIT Bombay from July 2014 and BITS Pilani from August 2014 are offering courses using the edX platform.

Looking to the educational industry, NIIT Limited India lunched its Interactive Classrooms @ Home - a unique technology enabled learning solution unveiled by NIIT Mind Champion Vishwanathan Anand in Pune.

However no such visible MOOC in Odia language like any other Indian languages are seen in market to attract the large scale motivated students. Hence the systematic architecture to Indian languages for massive open online course to our future generation is very much essential in order to fill the gap.

SAIL-MOOC:

On the basis of basic concept of MOOCs, here is an online course called "SAIL-MOOC- Systematic Architecture to Indian Languages Massive Open Online Course". It aims at large-scale participation and open (free) access via the internet. SAIL-MOOC emphasizes on the education to be provided in different Indian Languages primarily started from a classical regional language Odia and to be offered to other Indian Languages in latter stages. Odia Language course content will be useful to the language dependent user.

SAIL-MOOC provides customizable education in which participants are free to select any of the subjects and can create their own customized course. Participants are free to complete this course in any way they would like it to be.

It provides open access to the participants. For academic credits participants have to pay the fees depending upon the collaborating universities providing the credit. There is openness in sharing the work between each other for better understanding.

SAIL-MOOC is a cloud based online course. So it provides high scalability in terms of resources at any situations. On demand access are fulfilled by the cloud services which the users can use anytime anywhere.

Salient Features:

To blend the goal of attaining higher education the described system aims to incorporate the goal of facilitators, to include the role of university, to provide maximum benefit for the student and nothing but the least to empower the nation using mother tongue. Except this the other salient features of the system are:

- Understand the unique situations of learners through continual cognition.
- Accessible through different means of communication from desktop to Mobile.
- Try to solve the learners query beyond the syllabus.
- Proper management of the volume of learners.
- Resource Pooling.
- Increase the storage dynamically.
- For learners better understanding, video-graphs in 3-D effect and technology.

How to participate in an SAIL-MOOC?

To participate in SAIL-MOOC, participants have to complete online registration process. After the registration participants are provided with the workspace. Participants have been made available to all the details like the procedures, rules, list of courses and subjects available etc. Each course available will be open to all the participants irrespective of their age, qualification background etc. Participants will be provided with the information regarding the premium courses sponsored by Universities which offers Academic Credits to the participants.

The course material, reference material for particular course in Textual, Audio, Video form are available for free to all the participants. They can be easily downloaded. Schedules of live lectures, updates regarding the selected course like assessment test, assignments etc are

updated time to time to the participants on their workspace.

How SAIL-MOOC Works?

The whole process of course SAIL-MOOC is a circular and continual knowledge grown model. The model is divided into four different steps. These steps are prepared after understanding the students' requirements and also considering the proper execution of educational cycle for the subject.

The four steps are as follows –

- Flip Teaching (F-MOOC)
- Interactive Teaching (I-MOOC)
- Participatory Learning (P-MOOC)
- Consolation Learning (C-MOOC)

1.1 Flip teaching

Flip education is exact opposite of the traditional education. In flip education, what used to be a class work is done at home and in class room and what used to be homework (assigned problems) is now done in class. In this step participants watch and listen to the pre-recorded lectures, can go through presentations and study materials corresponding to their selected course. SAIL-MOOC will have these study material and pre-recorded audio/videos for the reference to the participants. Through Flip education participant actually have the preface of the subjects. That will ease them in understanding the topic in next step of Live Education.

In our flipped classroom: (a) the participant can become hostage to the pedagogy. (b) Here Lecturers may be divided into micro segments that matched participant's attention spans. (c) Students will all eagerly watch the videos and come to class ready to apply their knowledge in next level teaching.

1.2 Live Education and Interactive Teaching

In Interactive education, the system has a 'web video conferencing tool' to hold our classes remotely. In this, the Lecturers Teams got out of the building and spoke to a small group of students in weekly basis. Back in the weekly class, the subject specialist present their results in front of their fellow colleagues. When the subject specialist presentations over, again the course coordinator lectured to these remote students about next week's objectives.

Here our teachers and students to work together in small groups to solve a problem, a discussion ensues that not only serves in it to build more robust knowledge structures, but also to motivate. The teachers takes class, ask questions, giving something students to do, getting back what they done and assimilating himself in this web class, so that the pupil can decide what would be best to do next.

1.3 Participatory Learning

In order to encourage participatory teaching learning method, the 'SAIL-MOOC' constituent group takes a broad look at MOOCs as a paradigm of learning communities and open education. Participants are encouraged to share experiences, ideas, and challenges relating to large-scale, open, online learning experiences. Key topics would include distributed as well as centralized approaches in pedagogy and instructional design perspectives.

By getting a taste of what the participants experience, the 'SAIL-MOOC' better able to understand what might keep them from fully participating in the class and what it can do to overcome these apprehensions. Here, the customers involved himself as a harmonious participant through different means of participation forum like blog, chart and group

mail etc in a closed pedagogical discussion environment.

And the system though its inherent model case question strategies (a) geared to an online environment as an active participant (b) facilitate and debrief the case discussions within an LMS (Learning management system) (c) share testimonials and examples of successful strategies.

So the participatory teaching-learning circle encourages students to work cooperatively to construct meaning from what they have read and avoid focusing on a 'correct' interpretation of the text. The detail architecture of Participatory MOOC is given at Fig No.1

1.4 Consolation Learning:

Consolation Learning is not only an evaluation of learner knowledge acquisition component in the platform but also it broadly focuses on community and emergent learning. However, the system adopts automated testing, by way of multiple-choice quizzes, and peer reviews method by Crowd marking. By this, the participants work on a project (or projects) throughout their involvement in the MOOC. The projects receive student comments by peers designed around improvement or they are evaluated by a team. After the process the through the process of 'Crowd marking' (an online collaborative grading platform) the Consolation MOOC of SAIL-MOOC solves the midterm assessment bottleneck plaguing the education system.

However as more schools move toward offering credit for these vast online courses, the final set of examination of 'SAIL-MOOC' accepts a number of problem sets: implement a function to do this-or-that within certain design parameters.

SAIL-MOOC Consolation module includes a number of modular environments for final assessment of participant's knowledge acquisition and to ensure the MOOCs business quality. These are: (a) Homework gradation, (b) Exams feedbacks, (c) Number of feedback received through participatory education (d) Free version Certification receiving.

Challenges

The system would provide educational opportunities for Education through online mode for a large segment of the population. Irrespective of flexibility in of Age, Study Center, Time limit, Examinations, the system would raise its helping hand to those who are unable to afford Traditional University Education. Except this, the language department users and other stake holders also become beneficiaries to this system. However, lots of challenges are there to this system. In this system:

- Participants have to create their own content according to their course selection
- Digital literacy is necessary for participating to any course
- As the courses are customized there is no fixed time and duration specified for the completion of course so time and effort are required from participants

- It is organic, which means the course will take on its own trajectory
- Participants must self-regulate and set their own goals for the better understanding as well as completion of course.

Except this Course Contents, Infrastructure, Ensuring the accuracy of the cognitive query, evaluating learners understanding, and Availability mode of accessibility of devices a number of direct or indirect constraints would hamper the system performance in dynamic prospective.

Conclusion

There are many challenges that India has to come across while stepping ahead towards this innovation for local languages like Odia. So a strategic move, various new educational policies needs to be made. Further adopting the SAIL-MOOC architecture would help people to gain knowledge over a wide range of subjects. It narrows the educational barrier by providing course-contents in various Indian Languages. It provides unlimited availability of educational resources for better understanding. And the proposed Model has a vision to affect the Indian education system in localizing environment and resources.

Participatory MOOC as described refers to Fig No.1

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